

Kinetics and Mechanism of Base Catalysed Hydrolysis of *m*-Methoxybenzoic Acid Hydrazide

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The kinetics and mechanism of base catalysed hydrolysis of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide in aqueous sodium hydroxide over the range of 0.02-6.0 *M*, have been investigated spectrophotometrically at 70°. The reaction has been found to follow pseudo-first order rate law. The reaction leads to the formation of hydrazine and *m*-methoxybenzoic acid. Three cases of hydrolysis, applicable to three different ranges of NaOH concentrations were recognised. The activation parameters have been evaluated. The rate constants increase with increase in base concentration and attains optimum value at 3 *M*.

RECENTLY the kinetics of base catalysed hydrolysis of amides have been studied by a number of investigators¹. Similar effects on the kinetics of alkaline hydrolysis of formhydrazide have been reported², but so far no kinetic study have been made on the base catalysed hydrolysis of aromatic hydrazides.

The hydrazides are expected to undergo hydrolysis catalysed by both acid and base. The acid catalysed hydrolysis of hydrazides have been reported^{3,4,5}. This paper describes the studies of the kinetics and mechanism of the base catalysed hydrolysis of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide in an attempt to see its similarity with formhydrazide hydrolysis².

Experimental

m-Methoxy benzhydrazide was prepared by a known method⁶ and recrystallised from water, m.p. 94°. The alkaline solvents were made by diluting the fresh stock solution of NaOH (reagent grade).

All kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostated water bath and reaction rates were determined spectrophotometrically. The rate constants were measured from the appearance of hydrazine⁷ and the optical densities measured at 460 mμ on a SPEKOL.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants were found to increase with increase in the base concentration attaining maxima at 3.0 *M* and then decreased gradually (Table 1). This suggests change in mechanism after 3.0 *M* base concentration. Pseudo-first order rate constants in the hydrazide are independent of its change in concentration (Table 2).

Kinetics in dilute sodium hydroxide solutions: In the sodium hydroxide solution (< 3 *M*) *m*-CH₃O-C₆H₄-CONHNH₂ molecule and OH⁻ ion combine

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS OF BASE CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF *m*-METHOXYBENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDE AT 70°

NaOH <i>M</i>	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	NaOH <i>M</i>	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0.02	0.498	0.6	3.73
0.04	0.681	0.7	3.86
0.05	0.712	0.8	4.09
0.06	0.899	0.9	5.05
0.08	1.020	1.0	6.31
0.10	1.490	1.5	6.38
0.20	2.240	2.0	8.96
0.30	2.670	3.0	9.41
0.40	2.880	4.0	9.04
0.50	3.280	5.0	8.63
		6.0	7.94

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CHANGE OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION ON HYDROLYSIS OF *m*-METHOXYBENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDE SOLUTION AT 70°

Hydrazide × 10 ⁻⁴ <i>M</i>	NaOH <i>M</i>	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
2.344	0.5	3.283
1.758	0.5	3.223
1.172	0.5	3.289

to form complex (1) which decomposes slowly to form product (2).

Rate laws and k are given by

$$-\frac{d(\text{Hy})}{dt} = K (A^-) \quad (3)$$

$$-\frac{d(\text{Hy})}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} (\text{Hy}) \quad (4)$$

$$K = \frac{(A^-)}{(A)} \times \frac{\nu A^-}{\nu A a_{\text{OH}^-}} \quad (5)$$

where $A = m\text{-CH}_3\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHNH}_2$,

Hy = total hydrazide ($A + A^-$),
 ν = activity coefficient, a = activity.

The overall rate constants k_{obs} is combined with K and k .

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{K} + \frac{1}{kK} \frac{\nu A^-}{\nu A a_{\text{OH}^-}} \quad (6)$$

A plot of $\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}}$ vs. $\frac{\nu A^-}{\nu A a_{\text{OH}^-}}$ gives a straight line with a slope $\frac{1}{kK}$ and intercept $\frac{1}{K}$ (Fig. 1). The values of a_{OH^-} were assumed to be equal to those of mean

Fig. 1

activity ($a_{\pm}$) of NaOH calculated by using mean activity coefficient obtained by interpolation from the reported data⁶. The values of νA^- were calculated from the approximate Debye-Huckel equation.

$$\log \nu A^- = -0.510 Z^2 \frac{I^{1/2}}{(1 + 1.15 I^{1/2})}$$

where Z is the valency of A^- (equal to unity) and I the ionic strength of aqueous NaOH solution.

A good extrapolation was obtained giving $K = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and using this value of K , the slope gives $k = 0.333$. Consequently, the linear plot indicates that in the region of NaOH concentration lower than *ca.* 3.0 mole the reaction scheme is given by equations 1 and 2, the rate determining step being the unimolecular decomposition of the complex (Fig. 2).

Above *ca.* 3.0 mole, $\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}}$ decreases linearly with increasing $[\text{NaOH}]$. Thus, the base catalysed hydrolysis would proceed by equation (1) in these regions of NaOH, the changes of hydration number being disregarded².

Kinetics in moderately concentrated sodium hydroxide solutions: The reaction scheme for base catalysed hydrolysis of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide in moderately concentrated NaOH solution is given by

It is observed from the plot k_{obs} vs. OH^- that k_{obs} is nearly constant in the narrow range of $[\text{NaOH}]$ *ca.* 3.0 *M* and further decreases linearly with increasing concentration of sodium hydroxide. Thus hydrolysis of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide would proceed by equation (7), in these region of $[\text{NaOH}]$, the change of hydration number being disregarded.

Correlation of k_{obs} with acidity function H_- : As suggested by Yagil and others⁹, these results belong to the group containing reactions expected to give a linear plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs. $H_- + \log C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ with unit slope. This plot shown in Fig. 2 together with the Zucker-Hammett type plot $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs. H_- indicate

Fig. 2. Yagil plot for alkaline hydrolysis of *m*-methylbenzoic acid hydrazide at 70°.

that the two linear parts can be obtained with slope deviating greatly from unity with boundary points between them. As suggested by Rochester in equation (8),

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} - H_- = 'V' \log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + \text{constant} \quad (8)$$

for the reactions in strongly basic media, 'V' parameter is evaluated.

The parameter 'V' in the above equation is the slope of the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}} - H_-$ vs. $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (Fig. 3). These parts correspond to two types of hydrolysis mechanism.

Fig. 3

References

1. R. H. DEWOLFE and R. O. NEWCOMB, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1971, 36, 3870.
2. M. MASHIMA and F. IKEDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, 46, 1371.
3. M. H. JAGDALE and A. Y. NIMBAKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 788.
4. M. H. JAGDALE and A. Y. NIMBAKAR, *J. Shivaji Univ. (Science)*, 1975, 15, 41.
5. M. H. JAGDALE and A. Y. NIMBAKAR, *Acta Cientia Indica*, 1976, 2, 336.
6. P. A. S. SMITH, "Organic Reactions", ed. ROGER ADAM, John Wiley, New York, 1946, p. 367.
7. W. W. GEORGE and J. D. CHRISP, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 2006.
8. G. AKERLOF and G. KRCHLES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 63, 620.
9. M. AUBAR, M. BOSTELSKY, D. SAMUEL, and G. YAGIL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 2380.